

Renewable Energy Consumption, CO2 Emissions, and Economic Growth in Morocco: ARDL Approach

La consommation des énergies renouvelables, les émissions de CO2 et la croissance économique au MAROC : Approche ARDL

LIOUAEDDINE Mariem

Enseignante chercheuse

Faculté des Sciences Juridiques, Economiques et Sociales

Université Ibn Tofaïl

Laboratoire des sciences économiques et politiques publiques

Maroc

LAMSAF Marzouqa

Doctorante

Faculté des Sciences Juridiques, Economiques et Sociales

Université Ibn Tofaïl

Laboratoire des sciences économiques et politiques publiques

Maroc

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Abstract

This study explores the causal relationships between renewable energy consumption, CO2 emissions, and economic growth in Morocco from 1980 to 2019. We utilized the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) approach to analyze both the long-term and short-term dynamics among these variables. Our findings reveal an inverted U-shaped relationship between GDP and CO2 emissions, indicating that CO2 emissions increase with GDP up to a certain inflection point, beyond which emissions start to decrease. This pattern highlights the significance of environmental considerations in economic planning. In the short term, our analysis suggests that the long-term equilibrium adjusts by about 29% following a short-term shock. This means that when per capita CO2 emissions deviate from their equilibrium level, they are likely to adjust by 29% annually to return to equilibrium. Over the long term, we found that CO2 emissions are primarily driven by GDP and renewable energy consumption. These findings lend support to the growth hypothesis, emphasizing the pivotal role of economic and energy factors in shaping environmental outcomes.

Keywords: Renewable energies; Economic growth; CO2 emissions; Morocco's development; ARDL approach.

Résumé

Cette étude examine les liens de causalité entre la consommation d'énergies renouvelables, les émissions de CO2 et la croissance économique au Maroc de 1980 à 2019. À cette fin, nous avons utilisé l'approche de lag distribué autorégressif (ARDL) pour explorer la causalité à long et à court terme entre ces variables. Nos résultats révèlent une relation en forme de U inversé entre le PIB et les émissions de CO2. Cela signifie que les émissions de CO2 augmentent initialement avec l'augmentation du PIB jusqu'à atteindre un point d'inflexion, après lequel elles diminuent progressivement, soulignant ainsi les implications environnementales de la croissance économique. De plus, les résultats indiquent que l'équilibre à long terme s'ajustera d'environ 29 % suite à un choc à court terme. Cela suggère que lorsque les émissions de CO2 par habitant s'écartent de leur niveau d'équilibre, elles s'ajusteraient de 29 % par an. À long terme, nous avons constaté que les émissions de CO2 sont principalement influencées par le PIB et la consommation d'énergies renouvelables. Ces découvertes soutiennent l'hypothèse de croissance, mettant en lumière l'impact significatif des facteurs économiques et des énergies renouvelables sur les résultats environnementaux.

Mots clés: Energies renouvelables; Croissance économique; Emissions de CO2; Développement du Maroc; l'approche ARDL

Introduction

Amid growing concerns about the global environmental crisis, the strategic role of renewable energy continues to expand, especially in terms of energy security and sustainable development. Morocco, heavily reliant on fossil fuels, is at a critical energy and environmental crossroads. The country's primary energy consumption is mainly comprised of oil (62%), coal (22%), and natural gas (5%) (Allouhi et al., 2017; Kousksou et al., 2015). As a nation largely dependent on oil, Morocco is particularly vulnerable to fluctuations in fossil fuel prices and associated greenhouse gas emissions (GGE), which contribute significantly to global emissions (Kousksou et al., 2015).

Since the last comprehensive review by the International Energy Agency in 2014, Morocco's energy and climate policy has evolved considerably, reflecting a strong commitment to renewable energy and energy efficiency. These efforts align with international commitments such as the Paris Agreement and the United Nations COP22 conference held in Marrakech in 2016. In line with this strategy, Morocco aims to increase the share of renewable energy to 52% of its total electricity production by 2030 while reducing its CO₂ emissions by 17% compared to 2015 levels (Kousksou et al., 2015).

This research addresses the crucial question: What is the relationship between renewable energy consumption, economic growth, and CO₂ emissions in Morocco? To explore this issue, the study employs the robust methodological approach of the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model, known for its ability to analyze short and long-term relationships between dependent variables. Using this model, it's possible to assess the direct impact of renewable energy consumption on Morocco's economy and CO₂ emissions reduction, considering the dynamics of the country's socio-economic and demographic development.

The research is structured as follows: it begins with a literature review that establishes the theoretical and contextual framework, followed by a detailed presentation of the data and methodology, analysis of the results, and concludes with a synthesis of the findings, summarizing the implications for Morocco's energy and environmental policies. Through this research, we aim to actively contribute to the debate by offering fact-based perspectives.

1. Littérature review

1.1. The Relationship Between Renewable Energies and CO₂ Emissions

The global reliance on fossil fuels has sparked an urgent need for sustainable energy solutions in response to the critical challenges posed by climate change and greenhouse gas emissions.

There is a broad consensus among researchers that renewable energy technologies are crucial for mitigating environmental impacts and promoting sustainable development.

(Dincer & Rosen, 1999) discuss the intrinsic connection between energy use, environmental health, and sustainability, proposing that a truly sustainable society should completely transition to renewable energy sources due to their minimal environmental footprints. This perspective is further explored by (Dincer, 2000), who provides a detailed analysis of the environmental impacts associated with both traditional and renewable energies, advocating for a sustainable development path focused on clean energy.

(Kalogirou, 2004) investigates the detrimental environmental impacts of fossil fuels and champions solar energy as a viable alternative with minimal environmental drawbacks. This assertion is supported by empirical data on a strategic energy shift in Saarbrücken, Germany, which highlights the city's efforts in the 1980s to reduce energy consumption and CO₂ emissions through sustainable energy strategies.

(Granovskii et al., 2007) provide an economic analysis of replacing natural gas with wind and solar energy in the production of electricity and hydrogen. Their findings suggest that renewable energy sources can significantly lower the cost of emissions reduction compared to conventional energy sources, thus offering an economically viable pathway for pollution mitigation

Targeted studies in regions like Turkey and China shed light on the specific benefits and challenges of implementing renewable energy. Researchers such as (Bilen et al., 2008; Yu & Qu, 2013) emphasize how geographical and economic conditions influence the efficiency of renewable energy in reducing greenhouse gas emissions. (Yadoo & Cruickshank, 2012) detail the advantages of renewable energy systems for rural electrification in developing countries, demonstrating their potential in combating poverty and mitigating climate change.

(Amponsah et al., 2014) provide a comprehensive review of the greenhouse gas emissions throughout the lifecycle of renewable technologies, particularly noting the low emissions from offshore wind energy. Similarly, (Sapkota et al., 2014) use the LEAP model to project the long-term impacts of renewable energy in Nepal, highlighting a substantial potential for reducing household CO₂ emissions.

(Huang et al., 2021) studied the relationship between renewable energies (RE) and CO₂ emissions. Specifically, they explored the link between RE consumption and CO₂ emissions in a sample of major renewable energy-consuming countries from 2000 to 2015. Using the two-

step generalized method of moments (GMM) estimator, the empirical results suggested that RE has a significant and negative effect on CO₂ emissions.

1.2. The Relationship Between Economic Growth and CO₂ Emissions

The complex relationship between economic growth and environmental degradation has been the focus of numerous studies, particularly on how Gross Domestic Product (GDP) or per capita income influences environmental quality. The Environmental Kuznets Curve (EKC) hypothesis suggests that initially, economic growth leads to environmental degradation, but after reaching a certain income threshold, further growth results in improved environmental conditions. This hypothetical relationship typically takes the shape of an inverted U-curve, where environmental degradation increases at lower income levels but decreases as income continues to grow. While many studies support the EKC hypothesis, others question its validity and general applicability. Pioneering work by Grossman and Krueger in the early 1990s explored the relationship between air quality and economic growth, using data on air pollutants in Mexico. Their findings indicated that pollutants like sulfur dioxide and particulates initially increase with GDP per capita but begin to decrease once national income reaches about \$4,000 to \$5,000. This supports the notion that economic growth can mitigate pollution problems at higher income levels. In a related study, (Grossman & Krueger, 1991) also examined how pollution abatement costs in the American industry could influence the structure of international trade and investment, suggesting that economic considerations affect environmental outcomes.

(Friedl & Getzner, 2003) studied this relationship in Austria, concluding that economic growth was a primary driver of CO₂ emissions. Conversely, (Coondoo & Dinda, 2008) explored how income disparities between countries correlate with CO₂ emissions and found that income gaps significantly affect carbon emissions.

Other studies have challenged the universal applicability of the EKC. For example, (Maddison & Rehdanz, 2008) found a bidirectional causal relationship between per capita GDP and CO₂ emissions in most regions, except in Asia, indicating that higher incomes do not necessarily lead to reduced emissions in all contexts. (Galeotti et al., 2009) also highlighted that the EKC does not consistently apply to CO₂ emissions, suggesting that while cointegration tests may revive the concept of the EKC, it remains a fragile theoretical construct. Similarly, (Miah & al., 2010) demonstrated that in Bangladesh, CO₂ emissions more or less follow a straight line, suggesting that expectations of higher incomes may not reverse environmental degradation.

(Alam, 2014) examines the changes in economic structure and trends in carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions in relation to Bangladesh's per capita GDP over the period from 1972 to 2010. Using World Bank data and estimating the Environmental Kuznets Curve (EKC), the author finds that the "U" shape of the EKC does not exist. Furthermore, the rapid transition from agriculture to non-agricultural sectors and the emergence of services as the dominant sector in the economy show an upward trend in CO₂ emissions.

(Onofrei et al., 2022) examine the relationship between economic growth and CO₂ emissions in the 27 EU member states from 2000 to 2017. Using both qualitative and quantitative methods, including DOLS, unit root tests, and cointegration techniques, they find a long-term cointegration relationship. Their findings suggest that a 1% change in GDP results in a 0.072% change in CO₂ emissions. The study also highlights that higher income levels increase the demand for environmental protection and the need for policies to reduce emissions during economic growth. Ultimately, they conclude that only sustainable economic growth can reduce climate vulnerability.

1.3. The Relationship Between Renewable Energy Consumption and Economic Growth

Energy is often considered a crucial lever for wealth creation and economic development, with historical studies affirming its pivotal role in shaping economic trajectories. Empirical analyses primarily focus on the interaction between energy consumption, particularly renewable, and economic growth through various theoretical frameworks:

- Growth Hypothesis: This theory posits that increased energy consumption boosts economic growth both directly and indirectly, with causality flowing from energy use to economic expansion. According to this model, restricting energy consumption could hinder economic development.
- Conservation Hypothesis: It proposes a causality from GDP to energy consumption, suggesting that energy conservation initiatives and demand management do not impede economic growth.
- Feedback Hypothesis: This approach indicates bidirectional causality between GDP and energy consumption, revealing a symbiotic relationship where each influences the other.
- Neutrality Hypothesis: It postulates no causal link between energy consumption and economic growth, implying that energy conservation efforts do not significantly impact economic performance.

Extensive research has been conducted to explore the relationship between energy consumption and economic growth:

(Apergis et al., 2010) confirmed a bidirectional causal relationship in the short and long term between renewable energy consumption and economic growth in 13 countries, using error correction models and multivariate panel data.

(Apergis & Payne, 2011) identified a unidirectional causality from biomass energy consumption to real GDP in the United States between 1949 and 2007 using Toda-Yamamoto causality tests.

(Al-mulali et al., 2013) found a bidirectional relationship between renewable energy consumption and growth in 85 of the 108 studied countries from 1980 to 2009. They also noted that 79% of these countries showed a positive long-term relationship between renewable energy consumption and GDP growth.

(Shafiei & Salim, 2014) discovered bidirectional causality between economic growth and the consumption of renewable and non-renewable energies in 29 OECD countries from 1980 to 2011.

(Bhattacharya et al., 2016) highlighted the influence of renewable energies on economic growth in 38 high renewable energy consumption countries from 1991 to 2012, advocating for collaborative governmental and organizational action.

(Hassine & Harrathi, 2017) reported a cause-and-effect relationship between renewable energy consumption, real GDP, trade, and financial development in Gulf Cooperation Council countries from 1980 to 2012, suggesting that the use and exports of renewable energies could boost the economic growth of these nations.

(Khobai & Roux, 2018) established a long-term cause-and-effect relationship between renewable energy consumption and economic growth in South Africa from 1990 to 2014.

(Ivanovski et al., 2021) investigate the impact of renewable and non-renewable energy consumption on economic growth during the period from 1990 to 2015. The findings reveal that in OECD countries, non-renewable energy consumption boosts economic growth, whereas renewable energy consumption does not have a significant impact. In contrast, in non-OECD countries, both types of energy consumption contribute to economic growth.

(Bui Minh & Bui Van, 2023) explore the relationship between real GDP and renewable energy use in Vietnam, considering factors such as capital and labor, over the period from 1995 to 2019. Using the ARDL model and the Granger causality test with an error correction model,

their results show a unidirectional causality between renewable energy use and economic growth, indicating that this relationship persists in the long term.

The analysis of various studies on the relationship between energy consumption, particularly renewable, and economic growth illuminates complex and variable interactions. Theories ranging from growth to neutrality reveal diverse dynamics depending on geographical and economic contexts. Evidence of bidirectional causality underscores a significant interdependence between energy and the economy, indicating that energy policies must be carefully designed to support economic growth while considering environmental imperatives.

1.4. The Relationship Between Economic Growth, Renewable Energies, and CO2 Emissions

The latest research in this field integrates and simultaneously examines the dynamics between economic growth and energy consumption, as well as economic growth and environmental pollution, using advanced econometric techniques within a unified analytical framework. However, the findings from these studies remain diverse, primarily due to variations in the data used, the periods studied, and the methodological approaches adopted. The development of the renewable energy sector could catalyze the modernization of the global energy sector to achieve sustainability goals set by policymakers. Economic growth plays a crucial role by providing the necessary resources for research and development of technologies and infrastructure for renewable energy (Karaipekli et al., 2007).

In their respective studies, various researchers have explored the relationship between energy consumption and economic growth with mixed results. For instance, in the United States, (Sari et al., 2008) assessed the impact of different energy sources on industrial production and employment, finding mixed long-term effects. (Sadorsky, 2009) analyzed the impact of renewable energy consumption on economic growth in emerging and G7 countries, finding a positive relationship between GDP, emissions, and increased consumption of renewable energy.

(Apergis & Payne, 2010), as well as (Apergis et al., 2010), confirmed a bidirectional causality between non-hydro renewable energy consumption and economic growth in a panel of OECD countries, and explored the relationship between nuclear energy, renewable energy, and economic growth, revealing varied short and long-term impacts on CO2 emissions. These studies demonstrate the complexity of the relationships between different types of energy and

economic indicators, emphasizing the importance of a nuanced approach to understanding and leveraging the potential of renewable energies in the context of global economic development. (Salim & Rafiq, 2012) used FMOLS, DOLS, and Granger causality tests to assess the relationship between renewable energy consumption and GDP in several countries, including Brazil, China, India, Indonesia, the Philippines, and Turkey from 1980 to 2006, concluding that renewable energy consumption is significantly influenced by income in both the short and long term.

(Ocal & Aslan, 2013) analyzed the causal relationship between renewable energy consumption, capital, labor, and economic growth during the period 1990 to 2010 in Turkey. They employed the autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) approach developed by Pesaran and al., along with Toda-Yamamoto causality tests. The results obtained using the ARDL approach indicate a negative impact of renewable energy consumption on economic growth. Additionally, the Toda-Yamamoto tests reveal a unidirectional causality from economic growth to renewable energy consumption.

(Zeb et al., 2014), using data from 1975 to 2010 for Bangladesh, India, Nepal, Pakistan, and Sri Lanka, examined the relationship between electricity production from renewable sources, GDP, CO₂ emissions, natural resource depletion, and poverty. Their results show bidirectional Granger causality between CO₂ emissions and natural resource depletion in Nepal and between energy production and poverty in Pakistan. They also highlighted Granger causality between energy production and poverty in Bangladesh and India, and between poverty and energy production in Sri Lanka.

(khoshnevis & Shakouri, 2017) conducted an empirical analysis of CO₂ emissions, economic growth, and energy consumption, focusing on renewable energies in Germany from 1975 to 2014. Utilizing cointegration tests, vector error correction models, and the VAR method, their findings indicated that the data did not support the Environmental Kuznets Curve, which posits a specific relationship between real GDP and CO₂ emissions. To estimate the shocks from renewable energy consumption, the study applied the dynamic impulse response function (IRF) test using the VAR method. Interestingly, the increasing share of renewable energy consumption in electricity production appeared to have no significant impact on the environment.

(Jeon, 2022) explored the interplay between energy-related CO₂ emissions, economic development, and renewable energy consumption across 48 U.S. states from 1997 to 2017. Employing advanced analytical techniques such as fixed-effects panel models and panel-

corrected standard errors, Jeon uncovered a significant inverted U-curve, aligning with the Environmental Kuznets Curve hypothesis. This curve illustrates how economic growth initially leads to environmental degradation before aiding environmental improvement. The study also highlighted the crucial role of renewable energy use, alongside electricity and primary energy prices, in reducing emissions. Additionally, it noted that heating days tend to increase emissions. A particularly innovative aspect of Jeon's work was the use of panel quantile regression models, which shed light on how the impacts of various factors on CO₂ emissions vary across different emission intensity levels. The results strongly emphasized the environmental benefits of promoting renewable energies and suggested that using energy pricing as a policy tool could be an effective strategy for reducing emissions.

One of the latest contributions to the literature on the relationship between economic growth and renewable energies is the work of (Nuță et al., 2024). This study examines the complex dynamics between economic expansion and carbon emissions, highlighting the challenges posed by industries heavily reliant on fossil fuels. The research underscores how primary sectors, often more energy-intensive, significantly contribute to environmental pressure compared to more energy-efficient tertiary sectors. Through an in-depth analysis covering emerging nations in Europe and Asia from 1995 to 2019, the study investigates the interplay between urban development, financial growth, the adoption of renewable energies, and structural changes in industries to mitigate environmental damage. Utilizing advanced statistical methods such as feasible generalized least squares (FGLS) and panel-corrected standard errors (PCSE), the findings argue for growth strategies that prioritize sustainable urbanization. Emphasizing the critical need for a shift towards a greener energy paradigm, the study highlights the urgency of moving away from traditional fossil fuel-based models to embrace renewable energy sources, thus promoting a more sustainable and environmentally friendly economic trajectory.

(Khan et al., 2024) have undertaken a significant study to examine the crucial influence of renewable energies, urbanization, and financial growth on environmental health across South Asian Association for Regional Cooperation (SAARC) countries, including Afghanistan, Bangladesh, Bhutan, Pakistan, Sri Lanka, Nepal, the Maldives, and India, spanning from 1990 to 2019. By employing a panel quantile regression method, the study assesses how the use of renewable energies, monetary circulation, urban growth, and natural resources impact carbon emissions and economic progress.

The findings indicate that the use of renewable energies significantly reduces CO₂ emissions, particularly at higher quantiles. Urbanization emerges as a positive force for GDP growth, while the exploitation of natural resources boosts both the GDP and CO₂ emissions. Interestingly, monetary supply supports GDP growth at lower quantiles but diminishes it at higher quantiles. This research underscores the critical need to support renewable energies and smart urban planning to achieve a harmonious balance between economic growth and environmental preservation in SAARC nations.

The literature review highlights the complex and multidimensional links between renewable energy consumption, economic growth, and CO₂ emissions. It reveals that adopting renewable energy can play a key role in reducing greenhouse gas emissions while supporting economic growth. However, the outcomes of studies vary widely depending on geographic and economic contexts and the methodologies used. The majority of studies support a positive relationship between the adoption of renewable energy and the reduction of CO₂ emissions as well as a boost in economic growth, thanks to technological innovations and supportive policies.

While existing studies provide valuable insights into the interactions between renewable energy consumption, economic growth, and CO₂ emissions, few have focused specifically on the Moroccan context using advanced econometric approaches such as the ARDL. Morocco, with its ambitious commitments to renewable energies and unique economic and environmental characteristics, provides a distinctive field of study to examine these dynamics. Moreover, there is a need for research that explores the long-term effects of renewable energy policies on the country's economic structure, as well as the implications of these policies on reducing regional disparities in energy access and economic development. Utilizing the ARDL approach, this study aims to fill this gap by providing a detailed and contextualized analysis of the short and long-term causality between these variables in Morocco.

2. Variables and analysis methods

2.1. Presentation of Variables and Description of Data

This analysis utilizes annual data recorded between 1980 and 2019. This specific time frame was chosen simply because the required data were not available for earlier periods. The use of quarterly statistics could have allowed for more sophisticated modeling, but such statistics are not available for some of the variables involved. The variables have been obtained or transformed into per capita data to account for changes in variables that are dependent on modifications in population structure. The variables included in the analysis are as follows:

- GDP per capita : This is the primary indicator of growth and the most commonly used measure. The GDP series are in constant 2000 US dollars, adjusted for purchasing power parity (PPP), with data sourced from the World Bank's World Development Indicators (WDI).
- CO2 emissions per capita : These are measured in metric tons per capita and are obtained from the BP Statistical Review of World Energy - Main Indicators.
- Renewable Energy (ER) per capita : Represents renewable energy consumption, measured in metric tons per capita. It is constructed from the variable for final energy consumption in metric tons and the variable for renewable energy consumption (as a percentage of total final energy consumption) drawn from the World Bank's World Development Indicators (WDI). This variable is interpolated for the 1980s.

Data on CO2 emissions and renewable energy consumption are available and can be obtained in two forms, observed and corrected. Data on observed energy consumption represent the energy consumed in a given year, and observed CO2 emissions similarly represent the emissions calculated for that year.

Finally, all variables are transformed into natural logarithms, as this helps to minimize fluctuations in data series and measure approximate growth rates when taking logarithmic differences. This transformation is a standard procedure in econometric analysis to stabilize variance and improve the interpretability of growth rates across different datasets.

Table 1: Description of Econometric Model Variables

Variable	Description	Data Source	Period
CO2_cap	Natural logarithm of CO2 emissions per capita (metric tons per person)	BP Statistical Review of World Energy - Main Indicators	1980-2019
ER_cap	Natural logarithm of renewable energy consumption per capita	The World Bank	1980-2019
GDP	Natural logarithm of GDP per capita	The World Bank	1980-2019
GDP2	Natural logarithm of GDP per capita squared	The World Bank	1980-2019

Source: Authors

2.2. Methodology

The methodology adopted for addressing our research question is the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model, initially introduced by Pesaran et al. in 1999 and further developed in 2001. Firstly, the ARDL approach is particularly suitable for small sample sizes. Indeed, the Johansen cointegration method requires a large number of observations for reliable estimation. Additionally, the ARDL test can be used with non-stationary time series without the constraint of having the same order of integration. It allows for cointegration testing simultaneously on variables integrated of order 1 (I(1)) and variables of order 0 (I(0)), which is not possible with other tests.

Another advantage of this model is that it can simultaneously address short-term effects and long-term dynamics, yielding more reliable results compared to other tests in these scenarios. Due to these econometric benefits, the ARDL method was utilized in this research to assess the long-term and short-term relationships between macroeconomic indicators.

To select the optimal ARDL model, we will use the Schwarz Information Criterion (SIC), which aims to identify the model that can provide statistically significant results with the fewest parameters possible.

We propose to estimate an ARDL model for the following function (in linear functional form):

$$CO2_{cap} = f(ER_{cap}, GDP, GDP^2)$$

If we aim to capture the short-term and long-term effects of the aforementioned explanatory variables on CO2 emissions, the representation of the function using the ARDL model will be:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta \ln CO2_{cap_t} = & \alpha_0 + \sum_{i=1}^p \alpha_{1i} \Delta \ln CO2_{cap_{t-i}} + \sum_{j=0}^q \alpha_{2j} \Delta \ln ER_{cap_{t-j}} + \sum_{j=0}^q \alpha_{3j} \Delta \ln GDP_{t-j} \\ & + \sum_{j=0}^q \alpha_{4j} \Delta \ln GDP_{t-j}^2 + \beta_1 \ln CO2_{cap_{t-1}} + \beta_2 \ln ER_{cap_{t-1}} + \beta_3 \ln GDP_{t-1} \\ & + \beta_4 \ln GDP_{t-1}^2 + \varepsilon_t \end{aligned}$$

With :

Δ : First difference operator;

α_0 : Constant ;

$\alpha_{1...4}$: Short term effects;

$\beta_{1...4}$: Long term effects;

ε_t : Error term (white noise).

When multiple variables integrated of different orders (I(0), I(1)) are available, the cointegration test by Pesaran et al. (2001) is utilized. After determining the optimal lags, the testing procedure continues by comparing the obtained Fisher values with the critical values (limits).

However, estimating an error correction model can help confirm the existence of cointegration among the variables. For the purposes of our analysis, the model will be structured as follows:

$$\Delta \ln CO2_cap_t = \alpha_0 + \sum_{i=1}^p \alpha_{1i} \Delta \ln CO2_cap_{t-i} + \sum_{j=0}^q \alpha_{2j} \Delta \ln ER_cap_{t-j} + \sum_{j=0}^q \alpha_{3j} \Delta \ln GDP_{t-j} + \sum_{j=0}^q \alpha_{4j} \Delta \ln GDP_{t-j}^2 + \theta u_{t-1} + \varepsilon_t$$

3. Empirical results

We used Eviews 10 software to conduct the tests for our study. This software, designed for econometric analysis, enables us to perform a variety of tests that were not available in previous versions of the software.

3.1. Stationarity of the series

The first and most fundamental step in almost all econometric analyses of time series data is to test for the stationarity or non-stationarity of the data. In this study, however, we apply the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) and Phillips-Perron (PP) stationarity tests, the results of which are presented in Tables 2 and 3 below.

Table 2: Augmented Dickey Fuller Test (ADF)

Variable	A level I(0)		In first differences I(1)	
	t-statistic	Prob	t-statistic	Prob
CO2_cap	-3.188734	0.1015	-5.963375	0.0001
ER_cap	-3.640107	0.0392	-5.552919	0.0003
GDP	-3.183744	0.1041	-5.284400	0.0006
GDP2	-2.378993	0.3832	-5.282184	0.0006

Source: Authors (our estimates on EViews 10)

Table 3: Phillips Perron (PP) test

Variable	A level I(0)		In first differences I(1)	
	Adj.t-stat	Prob	Adj.t-stat	Prob
CO2_cap	-3.142888	0.1110	-7.075264	0.0000
Er_cap	-3.740316	0.0312	-6.641200	0.0000
GDP	-3.576664	0.0451	-5.546052	0.0003
GDP2	-3.528339	0.0502	-5.362311	0.0005

Source: Authors (our estimates on EViews 10)

The results indicate that the variables are stationary at first difference and their evolution fluctuates around several means. However, none of them are integrated of order 2. Therefore, it is feasible to use the ARDL model for our analysis.

3.2. Test de cointégration

To apply the Pesaran cointegration test, we will follow two steps:

3.2.1. Optimal Lag Selection and ARDL Model Estimation Using the Schwarz Information Criterion (SIC)

We will use the Schwarz Information Criterion (SIC) to select the optimal ARDL model, which is the one that can provide statistically significant results with the fewest possible parameters. Below are the results from the estimation of the selected optimal ARDL model.

Table 4: Optimal Model Obtained: ARDL (1, 0, 0, 3)

Variable	Coefficient	Std.Error	t-statisti	Prob
CO2_cap(-1)	0.710767	0.088532	8.028398	0.0000
ER_cap	1.108617	0.296513	3.738851	0.0008
GDP	0.535263	0.165537	3.233502	0.0030
GDP2	-0.027510	0.010525	-2.613915	0.0140
GDP2(-1)	0.000635	0.002348	0.270642	0.7886
GDP2(-2)	-0.001745	0.002258	-0.772789	0.4459
GDP2(-3)	0.004369	0.001710	2.554900	0.0161
C	-3.546270	0.888507	-3.991269	0.0004
R-squared	0.994043	F-statistic		691.2777
Adjusted R-squared	0.992605	Prob (F-stat)		0.000000

		Durbin-Watson stat	1.837153
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Source: Authors (our estimates on EVIEWS 10)

*dependent variable: CO2 per capita

Figure 1: SIC Graphic values

Source: Authors (our estimates on EVIEWS 10)

As can be seen in the figure 1, the ARDL (1, 0, 0, 3) model is the most optimal among the 20 others presented, as it offers the lowest Schwarz value. Additionally, the R-squared and adjusted R-squared parameters are 0.994043 and 0.992605 respectively, indicating that the model is well-fitted.

3.2.2. Fisher F Cointegration Bounds Test

This step aims to verify the existence of a long-term relationship between the variables in our specified model. Cointegration exists when the Fisher statistic value exceeds the upper bound value. The results of the cointegration test presented in Table 5 thus demonstrate the existence of cointegration among the variables of our model. As a result, we are able to estimate both the short-term and long-term relationships.

Table 5 : Results of the ARDL Bound-Test

F-Bounds Test		Null Hypothesis: No levels relationship		
Test Statistic	Value	Critical threshold	Lower terminal I(0)	Top terminal I(1)
F-statistic	8.679573	10%	2.37	3.2
K	3	5%	2.79	3.67
		2.5%	3.15	4.08
		1%	3.65	4.66

Source: Authors (our estimates on EVIEWS 10)

The results of the cointegration tests allow us to strongly reject the null hypothesis that suggests there is no cointegration among the variables. The F-statistic value of 8.679573, which exceeds the upper bound of 4.66, clearly demonstrates the existence of a long-term relationship between renewable energy consumption per capita, GDP, GDP squared (GDP2), and CO2 emissions.

The cointegration tests show a strong long-term relationship between renewable energy consumption, GDP, squared GDP, and CO2 emissions in Morocco. The high F-statistic confirms this connection, providing valuable insights for policymakers in their strategic planning (Ben Jebli & Ben Youssef, 2017). Understanding the causality between these variables will help identify key drivers and feedback mechanisms, which are essential for developing effective and sustainable policies. Further research and model validation will enhance the reliability and applicability of these findings.

Initially, our focus is on examining the causality among the variables, including the causal effects of the following variables: CO2 per capita (CO2_cap), renewable energy per capita (ER_cap), GDP, and GDP squared (GDP2).

3.3. Short-and long-term relationship

3.3.1. Short-Term Dynamics Analysis

The short-term analysis includes the incorporation of an error correction model (ECM) term, estimated within the framework of the ARDL model. The ECM identifies the speed of adjustment needed to return to equilibrium in the event of a deviation. A priori, the ECM coefficient is expected to be negative and statistically significant to ensure that the variables converge towards equilibrium.

Table 5: Short-Term Outcome Estimation

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob
D(GDP2)	-0.027510	0.004349	-6.325871	0.0000
D(GDP2(-1))	-0.002624	0.001616	-1.624444	0.1151
D GDP2(-2))	-0.004369	0.001443	-3.027387	0.0051
CointEq(-1)*	-0.289233	0.0411558	-7.027359	0.0000

Source: Authors (our estimates on EViews 10)

*ECM

According to the results shown in Table 5, the coefficient of the ECM is negative and significant (-0.28). This confirms the existence of a short-term equilibrium relationship among the variables in the cointegration test and also indicates that the estimated model is stable. It demonstrates how the model's variables converge towards a long-term equilibrium after experiencing a short-term shock.

The findings indicate that CO₂ emissions per capita adjust by 29% annually to return to their equilibrium level after a short-term shock, suggesting a quick adjustment dynamic. The model shows that variables converge to a long-term equilibrium with significant coefficients for the lagged GDP squared (PIB2), representing the expected short-term elasticities. In summary, the 29% annual adjustment rate towards long-term equilibrium after a short-term shock highlights the resilience and responsiveness of the system in Morocco. While this rapid adjustment is a positive sign, it should be complemented with proactive policies aimed at achieving sustainable long-term reductions in CO₂ emissions.

3.3.2. Analysis of Long-Term Dynamics

The results of the long-term relationship estimation, presented in Table 6, align with those of the short-term relationship. The consumption of renewable energy and economic growth in Morocco have a positive effect on CO₂ emissions. Conversely, the squared GDP per capita has a negative effect on CO₂ emissions per capita.

Table 6: Long-Term Estimation

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Stat	Prob
ER_cap	3.832955	1.111889	3.447246	0.0018
GDP	1.850629	0.687030	2.693666	0.0116
GDP2	-0.083845	0.042012	-1.995738	0.0554
C	-12.26095	3.540929	-3.462636	0.0017
EC = CO2_cap - (3.8330*ER_cap + 1.8506*GDP - 0.0838*GDP2 - 12.2609)				

Source: Authors (our estimates on EViews 10)

A 1% increase in renewable energy consumption results in a 3.83% rise in per capita CO₂ emissions. Although this outcome seems paradoxical, it can be explained by several factors. During the study period, Morocco was likely undergoing an energy transition, which required initial investments in renewable infrastructure that were carbon-intensive (Slimane et al., 2022). Additionally, an increase in renewable energy consumption can lead to higher emissions if it coincides with a rise in overall energy demand without a corresponding reduction in fossil fuel sources. Furthermore, a 1% increase in GDP leads to a 1.85% rise in per capita CO₂ emissions, suggesting that economic growth in Morocco has been associated with higher CO₂ emissions, which is consistent with the initial phase of economic development. During this phase, industrialization, urbanization, and increased fossil fuel consumption contribute to higher emissions (Benali & Benabbou, 2023).

Lastly, a 1% increase in squared per capita GDP reduces CO₂ emissions by 0.08%, supporting the Environmental Kuznets Curve (EKC) hypothesis. This hypothesis suggests that after reaching a certain income level, economic growth leads to greater environmental awareness, the adoption of cleaner technologies, and the implementation of stricter environmental policies, all of which help to reduce emissions.

3.4. CUSUM and CUSUMSQ Stability Tests

The final step in the ARDL estimation process is to check the stability of the parameters over the short and long term. A fundamental assumption of the classic regression model is that parameters remain constant across the sample.

The CUSUM test plots the CUSUM sequences along with critical lines to conduct the CUSUM test. The charts below display the plots for the CUSUM and CUSUMSQ tests. They indicate that both CUSUM and CUSUMSQ fall within a 5% significance interval. Therefore, we can conclude that the model is stable.

Figure 2: CUSUM stability test

Figure 3: CUSUMQ stability test

Source: Authors (our estimates on EViews 10)

The CUSUM and CUSUMQ test results confirm that the ARDL (1, 0, 0, 3) model's coefficients remain stable over time, staying within the critical values interval at a 5% significance level. This stability indicates that the model is statistically valid and reliable for analyzing the relationship between renewable energy consumption, GDP, squared GDP, and CO2 emissions. The consistent coefficients enhance the model's credibility, making it a robust tool for both short-term and long-term policy analysis and decision-making.

Conclusion

The current study examines the interplay between renewable energy consumption, economic growth, and CO2 emissions in Morocco from 1980 to 2019, using the ARDL approach. The results confirm the presence of an Environmental Kuznets Curve (EKC), demonstrating that emissions initially increase with per capita GDP, then decrease after reaching a tipping point, highlighting the effectiveness of sustainable development policies in place.

This study significantly contributes to existing literature by emphasizing the importance of renewable energy in reducing CO2 emissions in Morocco. Our findings align with (Huang et al., 2021), who also found that renewable energy consumption reduces CO2 emissions. However, our conclusions also reveal a long-term unidirectional causality not observed in all studies. For instance, (Alam, 2014) did not find an inverted U-shaped relationship in

Bangladesh, while (Onofrei et al., 2022) observed a long-term cointegration relationship between economic growth and CO2 emissions in EU countries.

Given these results, it is crucial for Moroccan policymakers to intensify efforts to promote investment in renewable energy. This includes not only achieving energy independence but also fostering sustainable and environmentally friendly economic growth (Khanniba et al., 2020). Investing in innovation and technology is essential to maximize the benefits of renewable energy (Bouyghrissi et al., 2022). Additionally, Morocco should consider enhancing international cooperation and actively participating in global climate initiatives. Public policies must support the development of necessary infrastructure and facilitate the effective integration of renewable energy. Public awareness and education also play a crucial role in this transition, requiring continuous efforts to ensure greater acceptance and commitment to a green economy. This study has methodological and contextual limitations. For example, limited data availability may restrict the analysis period and the granularity of available information. Additionally, regional specificities and variations in local policies can influence the results, limiting the generalizability of these conclusions to other contexts. Addressing these factors in more detail could improve the robustness of future research.

Future research should explore the impact of variables such as foreign direct investment, technological innovations, and specific policies on the relationship between renewable energy and economic growth. Comparative studies with other developing countries or regional analyses within Morocco could also provide additional insights. Examining the effects of specific policies, such as subsidies for renewable energy or carbon taxes, could offer practical recommendations for policymakers.

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